

Capping Off the Omnibus Policy on the Administration and Strengthening Capacities of Barangay Tanods: A Descriptive-Inferential Study

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Abstract

The objective of this research was to evaluate the performance of tanods from each barangay located in the first district of Isabela based on the guidelines of the Omnibus Policy on Administration and Strengthening the Capacities of Barangay Tanods from the DILG Memorandum Circular No. 2024-086. Specifically, it assessed the extent of involvement of barangay tanods fulfilling their duties and responsibilities. The study had 309 total participants who included 60 barangay officials, 100 barangay tanods and 149 residents of the community as the responding sample of this study. Descriptive-inferential design was used for the analysis and interpretation of the data collected. Further data for this study were obtained using validated and tested questionnaires. Based on the results of the research, the level of tanods' involvement in each of the first district municipalities in Isabela was consistently rated as "Highly Involved" by barangay officials compared to those rated by their respective community residents; however, barangay officials had a slightly higher average than did the community residents. Consequently, the barangay officials had a higher perception of tanod involvement in their duties than did the community residents perhaps because barangay officials supervise and closely work with the tanods.

Keywords: *Omnibus Policy, Administration, Capacities, Barangay Tanod, Peace and Order, Emergencies or disasters, descriptive-inferential design*

I. INTRODUCTION

Community security and public safety are vital to the development of any country and are necessary to provide stability for communities. Governments in all parts of the world recognize the role of implementing local law enforcement and community security programs for maintaining peace, preventing criminal activity, and gaining public confidence to its institutions.

The international community has developed numerous frameworks to guide community policing efforts globally, which call for participatory involvement at the grassroots level, the development of appropriate skill sets, and partnerships between official law enforcement agencies and community members as they work to address new emerging security concerns.

In the Philippines, the *barangay* or village provides the foundation of government and local security. Included in this system of government are the *barangay tanods*, who function to help enforce laws, promote peace, and provide assistance in times of emergency. However, their responsibilities are generally informal, with little formal policy support and a lack of comprehensive capacity building initiatives that would enhance the ability of *barangay tanods* to fulfil their duties.

The authority for *barangay tanods* derives from numerous national and local laws. The Barangay Peace and Order Committee (BPOC) must be created in accordance with the provisions of Republic Act No. 7160, otherwise known as the Local Government Code of 1991. *Barangay tanods* serve as the principal mechanism through which peace and order are maintained within the *barangay* and thus serve as critical components of the established BPOC (Republic Act No. 7160, 1991).

The Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) has put into practice Memorandum Circular No. 2003-42, which establishes the guidelines for providing benefits and incentives to *barangay tanods* in order to assist them in strengthening their skills as agents of peace and development.

Recently, the DILG issued Memorandum Circular No. 2024-086, which contains the Omnibus Policy on the Administration and Strengthening the Capacities of *Barangay Tanods* as Agents of Peace and Development. The purpose of this policy is to create a more professionalized workforce for *barangay tanods* and to prepare them for increased demands on local governance from the public (DILG, 2024).

Finally, Republic Act No. 6975, which established the DILG, provides that *barangay tanods* play an important role in assisting law enforcement agencies in preventing crime by providing community security and assisting with disaster relief efforts. Thus, this law indicates the need for an established, integrated policy framework to ensure that *barangay tanods* are properly trained, properly compensated, and properly deployed to provide community security and disaster relief services.

As explained by Sumad-On (2020) crime prevention process starts at the local government level to ensure the safety of all its residents. The *barangay tanod* plays the biggest role in this effort. The

study's results showed that *barangay tanod* are moderately effective in preventing crime, primarily due to poor execution of their duties. This includes conducting patrols, keeping watch for suspicious individuals, and identifying hazards in various locations. There is also a lack of proper training. The findings indicate that the *barangay tanod* face significant challenges in crime prevention due to inadequate transportation for patrolling, insufficient training in self-defense techniques, and a lack of essential equipment like batons and handcuffs.

Similarly, Bungalso et al. (2023) The researchers came to a conclusion that while the *barangay tanods* could perform their duties, they needed training and additional equipment so they can become more efficient. The study recommended conducting seminars about self-defense and first aid and giving the *tanods* the necessary tools so they can become more effective in maintaining peace and order in their community.

The research conducted by Lacanilao and Carpio (2025) indicated that *barangay tanods* enjoyed substantial community trust in their ability to apprehend suspects and manage traffic during emergencies and public functions. Nevertheless, the study also highlighted important challenges such as a lack of adequate resources and equipment, along with insufficient legal knowledge, which impede their effectiveness and safety while fulfilling their duties. The research suggested that specialized training, legal education, and the provision of necessary equipment would improve the capacity and efficiency of *barangay tanods* as first responders in their communities.

Supporting these findings, Alamban et al. (2024) The research concluded that *barangay tanods* require continuous professional development to enhance their crime prevention, emergency response, and hazard identification capabilities. The proposed Capability Training Program aims to strengthen their sense of duty and responsibility, improve first responder roles, and enhance patrolling and hazard identification skills. This study underscores the necessity for sustained investments in training and inclusive recruitment strategies to diversify and strengthen barangay law enforcement. It also provides a model for improving auxiliary police forces both locally and internationally by emphasizing structured training and knowledge enhancement programs.

Additionally, Dela Cruz et al. (2024) highlights the need for more training, awareness, and preparedness of *Barangay Tanods* in addressing such issues effectively. Some of the recommendations involve strengthening enforcement activities, expanding public information drives, equipping *Tanods* with the necessary resource requirements, and enhancing community partnership building. These findings present effective recommendations for designing intervention programs and policies to enhance the performance of *Barangay Tanods* in ensuring public safety, especially in high-stakes situations like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Finally, the study of Habiatan (2019) revealed that the Barangay Peace and Order Committee (BPOC) exhibited moderate participation in peace and order efforts, as reflected by an overall mean of 2.96, with Barangay Captains showing the highest level of involvement. Urban barangays demonstrated slightly greater participation compared to rural barangays. The study further noted that while the council is operational, sectors such as the youth, teachers, interfaith groups, senior citizens, and non-government organizations show lower involvement, and funding support for peace and order initiatives remains inconsistent. Overall, the research emphasizes that while the BPOC is functioning, opportunities exist to enhance participation, resource support, and community engagement.

The impact of *barangay tanods* as contributors to community peace and order has been highly underrated, primarily because there lacks both sufficient attention toward developing effective policies as well as investing in training for them. For this purpose and using existing or new legislation, the proposed solution includes creating policy-based opportunities to enhance the administration and capabilities of *barangay tanods* within the First District of Isabela by reducing any existing gaps in training or management processes, thus enabling *barangay tanods* to become better-equipped partners in delivering community security, service and good governance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to evaluate the performance of *tanods* in the first district of Isabela based on the requirements set forth in the DILG's Omnibus Policy for the Administration and Strengthening of *Barangay Tanod Capability* under Memorandum Circular No. 2024-086.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of involvement of *barangay tanods* in performing their duties and responsibilities as assessed by barangay officials and community residents relative to:
 - 1.1. Maintenance of peace and order;
 - 1.2. Emergencies or disasters;
 - 1.3. Handling complaints involving women;
 - 1.4. Handling complaints involving children
2. Is there a significant difference between the assessments of barangay officials and community residents regarding the level of involvement of *barangay tanods* in performing their duties and responsibilities in terms of the above dimensions when grouped according to municipality?

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In analyzing the data obtained through the administration of survey questionnaires, the weighted mean was used to quantify the *barangay tanods'* involvement in the performance of their duties and responsibilities in terms of Maintenance of peace and order, Emergencies or disasters, Handling complaints involving women, and Handling complaints involving children.

Four-Point Likert's Scale

Scale	Range	Description
4	3.25-4.00	Highly involved
3	2.50-3.24	Involved
2	1.75-2.49	Moderately Involved
1	1.00-1.74	Not involved

III. RESULT and DISCUSSION

1. Level of involvement of *barangay tanods* in performing their duties and responsibilities as assessed by barangay officials and community residents

Table 1

Mean and Interpretation on Level of involvement of *barangay tanods* in performing their duties and responsibilities as assessed by barangay officials and community residents in terms of Maintenance of Peace and Order

Maintenance of Peace and Order	Cabagan		San Pablo		Tumauini		Sto. Tomas		Delfin Albano		Sta. Maria		As A whole	
	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR
	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI								
1. Assist the barangay officials in the prevention of crime and the promotion of public safety;	4.00 HI	2.84 I	4.00 HI	3.71 HI	3.90 HI	3.74 HI	3.50 HI	3.77 HI	3.80 HI	3.87 HI	3.80 HI	3.65 HI	3.83 HI	3.60 HI
2. Conduct patrol/ronda within the barangay;	3.70 HI	1.88 MI	4.00 HI	3.37 HI	3.90 HI	3.64 HI	3.80 HI	3.49 HI	3.90 HI	3.77 HI	3.80 HI	3.37 HI	3.85 HI	3.25 HI
3. Report to the concerned barangay officials, or through Hotline local hotline the occurrence of any crime, fire, accident, public disturbance, environmental degradation activities, and other dents in the barangay;	3.70 HI	2.69 I	4.00 HI	3.65 HI	3.90 HI	3.68 HI	3.70 HI	3.61 HI	3.60 HI	3.64 HI	3.70 HI	3.49 HI	3.77 HI	3.46 HI
4. Monitor the presence and or activities of suspicious persons, and other lawless elements within their jurisdiction and report the same to the proper authorities or through hotline 911/local hotline;	3.60 HI	2.34 MI	4.00 HI	3.48 HI	3.90 HI	3.51 HI	3.20 I	3.39 HI	3.60 HI	3.51 HI	3.80 HI	3.52 HI	3.68 HI	3.29 HI
5. Conduct surveillance on crime breeding areas within the barangay/purok and report their observations/findings to the proper authorities, or through Hotline	3.70 HI	2.25 MI	4.00 HI	3.54 HI	3.80 HI	3.55 HI	3.10 I	3.52 HI	3.70 HI	3.73 HI	3.90 HI	3.40 HI	3.70 HI	3.33 HI

6. Assist the law enforcers in the execution of warrants and other judicial processes such as tracking the whereabouts of missing persons, arresting fugitives, and recovery of stolen properties	3.50 HI	2.28 MI	4.00 HI	3.26 HI	3.60 HI	3.26 HI	3.20 I	3.51 HI	3.80 HI	3.64 HI	3.40 HI	3.36 HI	3.58 HI	3.22 HI
7. Coordinate closely with the barangay officials and police/local authorities in the drive against all forms of crimes such as terrorism, smuggling, carnapping, drug trafficking, and pushing, illegal gambling, child abuse, crime against women, and all forms of vices and syndicated crimes;	3.70 HI	2.47 MI	4.00 HI	3.42 HI	3.50 HI	3.45 HI	3.60 HI	3.55 HI	3.50 HI	3.70 HI	4.00 HI	3.46 HI	3.72 HI	3.34 HI
8. Coordinate with homeowners association officials or any identified community leaders to ensure organized and proper implementation of their programs and activities;	3.50 HI	2.47 MI	3.70 HI	3.48 HI	3.60 HI	3.58 HI	3.60 HI	3.71 HI	3.30 HI	3.71 HI	3.90 HI	3.43 HI	3.60 HI	3.40 HI
9. Assist in the institutionalization of the Hotline 911 program;	4.00 HI	2.56 I	3.90 HI	3.64 HI	3.70 HI	3.58 HI	3.20 I	3.55 HI	3.50 HI	3.55 HI	3.80 HI	3.42 HI	3.68 HI	3.38 HI
10. Assist in the implementation of the fire code of the Philippines;	3.70 HI	2.50 I	3.60 HI	3.52 HI	3.60 HI	3.52 HI	3.20 I	3.55 HI	3.50 HI	3.70 HI	3.80 HI	3.33 HI	3.57 HI	3.35 HI
11. Detect all forms of fire hazards and other public safety hazards/ violations and institute corrective measures within their capability;	4.00 HI	2.59 I	3.60 HI	3.58 HI	3.60 HI	3.55 HI	3.60 HI	3.52 HI	3.60 HI	3.80 HI	3.90 HI	3.43 HI	3.72 HI	3.41 HI
12. Assist in facilitating the smooth flow of traffic; and	3.50 HI	2.38 MI	3.50 I	3.32 HI	3.50 HI	3.32 HI	3.30 HI	3.60 HI	3.60 HI	3.36 HI	3.50 HI	3.07 I	3.48 HI	3.18 I
13. Perform other functions as may be directed by the Punong Barangay	3.80 HI	2.69 I	3.50 HI	3.62 HI	3.50 HI	3.39 HI	3.00 HI	3.42 HI	3.30 HI	3.64 HI	3.90 HI	3.33 HI	3.50 HI	3.35 HI
Category mean	3.72 HI	2.46 MI	3.83 HI	3.51 HI	3.69 HI	3.52 HI	3.38 HI	3.55 HI	3.59 HI	3.66 HI	3.78 HI	3.41 HI	3.67 HI	3.35 HI

*BO- Barangay Officials, *CR-Community Residents, *HI-Highly Involved; I-Involved, MI-moderately involved

The table shows that overall, the category mean for Barangay Officials was 3.67 (Highly involved), while for Community Residents, it was 3.35 (Highly involved). This demonstrates that Barangay Officials consistently view the *tanods* as highly active and efficient in peacekeeping duties, whereas community residents recognize these efforts but perceive a lower level of involvement. This difference implies that while *tanods* are fulfilling their mandated responsibilities, their efforts are not always fully visible or felt by the community.

The findings of this study are similar to those of De Asis et al. (2024) and Alviola (2025). All three highlight the important role of *Barangay Tanods* in keeping peace and order in communities. The

previous studies and the current findings show that strong involvement and teamwork between *tanods* and community members directly support stability and safety in barangays. The results indicate that Barangay Officials rated the *tanods*' participation higher than community residents did. This difference suggests that greater community awareness and interaction are essential to improve the visibility and effectiveness of *tanods*. Therefore, this study supports the idea that ongoing public engagement, responsiveness, and transparency among *Barangay Tanods* are crucial for building trust, enhancing peacekeeping efforts, and encouraging participatory governance at the grassroots level.

Table 2

Mean and Interpretation on Level of involvement of *barangay tanods* in performing their duties and responsibilities as assessed by barangay officials and community residents in terms of Emergencies or Disasters

Tasks of Barangay Tanod during Emergencies or disasters	Cabagan		San Pablo		Tumauni		Sto. Tomas		Delfin Albano		Sta. Maria		As A whole	
	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR
	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI
1. Assist in the implementation of the Community-based Early Warning system.	4.00 HI	2.50 I	3.80 HI	3.58 HI	3.80 HI	3.52 HI	3.60 HI	3.57 HI	3.60 HI	3.65 HI	3.90 HI	3.43 HI	3.78 HI	3.37 HI
2. Conduct search and rescue operations	3.90 HI	2.50 I	3.80 HI	3.73 HI	3.60 HI	3.29 HI	3.50 HI	3.76 HI	3.40 HI	3.70 HI	4.00 HI	3.38 HI	3.70 HI	3.39 HI
3. Conduct first aid treatment of victims	3.60 HI	2.53 I	3.70 HI	3.61 HI	3.60 HI	3.57 HI	3.40 HI	3.57 HI	3.50 HI	3.50 HI	3.80 HI	3.33 HI	3.60 HI	3.35 HI
4. Assist in the clearing of debris and rehabilitation of roads, airfields, railways systems, ports and other key areas	4.00 HI	2.81 I	3.80 HI	3.49 HI	3.70 HI	3.76 HI	3.50 HI	3.76 HI	3.40 HI	3.70 HI	3.70 HI	3.43 HI	3.68 HI	3.49 HI
5. Assist in the conduct of preemptive and/or forced evacuation of individuals, groups, communities and livestock.	3.80 HI	2.50 I	3.80 HI	3.58 HI	3.50 HI	3.62 HI	3.20 HI	3.76 HI	3.70 HI	3.80 HI	3.70 HI	3.48 HI	3.62 HI	3.46 HI
6. Help in disseminating information and advisories to the public regarding evacuation and other measures in mitigating damages.	3.90 HI	2.66 I	3.90 HI	3.65 HI	3.40 HI	3.67 HI	3.60 HI	3.67 HI	3.80 HI	3.79 HI	4.00 HI	3.43 HI	3.77 HI	3.48 HI
7. Maintain public morale	3.90 HI	2.68 I	3.80 HI	3.52 HI	3.70 HI	3.43 HI	3.40 HI	3.71 HI	3.70 HI	3.65 HI	4.00 HI	3.29 HI	3.75 HI	3.38 HI
Category mean	3.87 HI	2.60 I	3.80 HI	3.59 HI	3.61 HI	3.55 HI	3.46 HI	3.69 HI	3.59 HI	3.69 HI	3.87 HI	3.39 HI	3.70 HI	3.42 HI

*BO- Barangay Officials,*CR-Community Residents, *HI-Highly Implemented; I-Implemented,MI-moderately implemented

The overall category mean for Barangay Officials was 3.70 (Highly Involved), while for Community Residents, it was 3.42 (Highly Involved). This shows that Barangay Officials perceive a stronger and more consistent implementation of emergency duties by *tanods* compared to the residents,

highlighting the importance of improving community awareness, transparency, and participation in disaster management efforts.

These findings are parallel to the study of Wakat (2024), which pointed out that despite challenges such as limited training and resources, *Barangay Tanods* remain highly involved and resilient in disaster risk reduction and management. Similarly, both studies emphasize that the commitment and active participation of *Tanods* are vital in ensuring community safety and preparedness, underscoring their indispensable role in local disaster response systems.

Table 3

Mean and Interpretation on Level of involvement of *barangay tanods* in performing their duties and responsibilities as assessed by barangay officials and community residents in terms of Handling complaints and incidents involving women

Handling Complaints and Incidents Involving Women	Cabagan		San Pablo		Tumauni		Sto. Tomas		Delfin Albano		Sta. Maria		As A whole	
	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR
	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI
1. Respond to gender-based violence cases brought to the barangay	4.00 HI	2.75 I	3.70 HI	3.67 HI	3.30 HI	3.38 HI	3.50 HI	3.63 HI	3.40 HI	3.75 HI	3.90 HI	3.30 HI	3.63 HI	3.41 HI
2. Assess the situation by getting information that can determine present and possible risks	3.90 HI	2.53 I	3.90 HI	3.79 HI	3.30 HI	3.52 HI	3.60 HI	3.74 HI	3.40 HI	3.85 HI	3.60 HI	3.25 HI	3.62 HI	3.45 HI
3. In case of an emergency, secure the victim in a safe place away from the place of incident and immediately contact the local social welfare and development officer	4.00 HI	2.72 I	3.90 HI	3.83 HI	3.90 HI	3.52 HI	3.70 HI	3.48 HI	3.80 HI	3.90 HI	3.90 HI	3.15 HI	3.87 HI	3.43 HI
4. If a third party is reporting the incident, check the completeness and correctness of data and for safety reasons, ask the assistance of the PNP	3.90 HI	2.97 I	3.90 HI	3.88 HI	3.70 HI	3.48 HI	3.30 HI	3.48 HI	3.50 HI	3.85 HI	3.70 HI	3.30 HI	3.67 HI	3.49 HI
5. In case of violence against women and their children (VAWC), inform the victim-survivor of her rights, the solution, and remedies available to her, and the process involved in her quest for justice	3.90 HI	2.78 I	3.90 HI	3.71 HI	3.30 HI	3.43 HI	3.40 HI	3.63 HI	3.70 HI	3.65 HI	4.00 HI	3.30 HI	3.70 HI	3.42 HI
6. Assist victims of VAWC in securing Barangay Protection Order (BPO) and accessing necessary needs	4.00 HI	2.66 I	3.90 HI	3.75 HI	3.10 I	3.29 I	3.60 HI	3.63 HI	3.80 HI	3.75 HI	4.00 HI	3.30 HI	3.73 HI	3.40 HI
7. Coordinate with and refer cases to the VAW Desk Officer or directly to the local social welfare and development	3.90 HI	2.56 I	3.90 HI	3.96 HI	3.40 HI	3.38 HI	3.40 HI	3.48 HI	3.70 HI	3.75 HI	3.70 HI	3.25 HI	3.67 HI	3.40 HI
8. Assist in the advocacies for the elimination of VAW in the community.	3.90 HI	2.66 I	3.90 HI	3.92 HI	3.40 HI	3.52 HI	3.60 HI	3.67 HI	3.40 HI	3.80 HI	3.90 HI	3.20 HI	3.68 HI	3.46 HI

9. Observe confidentiality at all times.	3.90 HI	2.88 I	3.80 HI	3.71 HI	3.30 HI	3.57 HI	3.40 HI	3.52 HI	3.40 HI	3.70 HI	3.70 HI	3.30 HI	3.58 HI	3.45 HI
Category mean	3.93 HI	2.72 I	3.87 HI	3.80 HI	3.41 HI	3.46 HI	3.50 HI	3.58 HI	3.57 HI	3.78 HI	3.82 HI	3.26 HI	3.68 HI	3.43 HI

The table presents the overall category mean of 3.68 (Highly involved) among Barangay Officials and 3.43 (Highly Involved) among Community Residents reveals that *Barangay Tanods* across the six municipalities are generally active in responding to, coordinating, and assisting in cases involving women, particularly those related to violence and abuse. However, the gap between the assessment of officials and residents indicates that while *tanods* may be performing their roles effectively from an administrative perspective, there remains a need to improve visibility, documentation, and awareness among community members regarding their interventions.

The results of this study support Mendoza (2025), who found that VAWC desk officers in Laguna showed strong role performance but limited visibility among community members. Similarly, Barangay Officials rated the *tanods* as highly involved, while residents gave lower ratings, indicating gaps in public awareness. Both studies highlight the need for continuous training, inter-agency coordination, and stronger community engagement to enhance transparency and trust in gender-based violence interventions.

Table 4

Mean and Interpretation on Level of involvement of barangay *tanods* in performing their duties and responsibilities as assessed by barangay officials and community residents in terms of Handling complaints and incidents involving children

Handling Complaints and Incidents Involving Children	Cabagan		San Pablo		Tumauini		Sto. Tomas		Delfin Albano		Sta. Maria		As A whole	
	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR	BO	CR
	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI	M/ DI
1. The Barangay Tanods are involved in recording reports in the barangay blotter, especially those related to child abuse and domestic violence while ensuring confidentiality.	3.90 HI	2.75 I	3.60 HI	3.67 HI	3.70 HI	3.38 HI	3.63 HI	3.40 HI	3.50 HI	3.75 HI	3.45 HI	3.30 HI	3.63 HI	3.37 HI
2. The Barangay Tanods conduct interviews with reporting individuals when the reporter is not the victim, to gather information about the incident.	3.60 HI	2.53 I	3.70 HI	3.79 HI	3.70 HI	3.52 HI	3.74 HI	3.00 I	3.60 HI	3.85 HI	3.30 HI	3.25 HI	3.61 HI	3.32 HI
3. The Barangay Tanods refrain from interviewing child victims and prioritize their medical needs and safety.	3.60 HI	2.72 I	3.80 HI	3.83 HI	3.50 HI	3.52 HI	3.48 HI	2.80 I	3.80 HI	3.90 HI	3.30 HI	3.15 I	3.58 HI	3.32 HI
4. The Barangay Tanods immediately coordinate with the DSWD or LSWDO and transfer the case to social workers for proper validation and assessment.	2.90 I	2.97 I	3.60 HI	3.88 HI	3.50 HI	3.48 HI	3.48 HI	2.70 I	3.50 HI	3.85 HI	3.10 I	3.30 HI	3.35 HI	3.36 HI

5. The Barangay Tanods assist in referring child victims to the police for proper investigation and ensure any arrest is done in coordination with authorities.	2.90 I	2.78 I	3.60 HI	3.71 HI	3.40 HI	3.43 HI	3.63 HI	2.90 I	3.20 I	3.65 HI	3.05 I	3.30 HI	3.30 HI	3.29 HI
6. Coordinate with the child's parents or guardians, considering the appropriate actions in cases of incest or abuse by guardians.	3.70 HI	2.66 I	3.70 HI	3.75 HI	3.20 I	3.29 HI	3.63 HI	2.90 I	3.40 HI	3.75 HI	3.15 I	3.30 HI	3.46 HI	3.27 HI
7. The Barangay Tanods do not participate in mediating or conciliating child abuse cases and inform parties that these cases are not subject to compromise.	3.10 I	2.56 I	3.60 HI	3.96 HI	3.00 I	3.38 HI	3.48 HI	3.10 I	3.60 HI	3.75 HI	3.35 HI	3.25 HI	3.36 HI	3.33 HI
8. The Barangay Tanods assist social workers during home visits and help monitor the child's and family's safety and well-being.	3.50 HI	2.66 I	3.70 HI	3.92 HI	3.10 I	3.52 HI	3.67 HI	2.90 I	3.70 HI	3.80 HI	3.30 HI	3.20 I	3.49 HI	3.33 HI
9. The Barangay Tanods maintain confidentiality in all stages of handling child-related complaints.	3.60 HI	2.88 I	3.60 HI	3.71 HI	3.40 HI	3.57 HI	3.52 HI	3.10 I	3.60 HI	3.70 HI	3.35 HI	3.30 HI	3.51 HI	3.38 HI
Category mean	3.42 HI	2.72 I	3.66 HI	3.80 HI	3.39 HI	3.46 HI	3.58 HI	2.98 I	3.54 HI	3.78 HI	3.26 HI	3.26 HI	3.48 HI	3.33 HI

*BO- Barangay Officials, *CR-Community Residents, *HI-Highly Involved; I-Involved, MI-moderately involved

The overall category mean of 3.48 (Highly Involved) among Barangay Officials and 3.33 (Highly Involved) among Community Residents indicates that *Barangay Tanods* across the six municipalities are generally engaged in addressing and managing child-related complaints, particularly through coordination with social workers, police authorities, and welfare agencies. However, the consistent pattern of lower ratings from residents compared to officials reveals a gap in public perception, highlighting that while *tanods* perform their duties according to policy, community awareness and participation in these processes remain limited.

This finding contrasts with Esquinas (2025), who reported only moderate levels of effectiveness in child protection services, thereby highlighting that *barangay tanods* in the first district of Isabela demonstrate relatively stronger involvement in preventing child abuse and promoting children's welfare.

Table 5

Test of Difference on the assessments of *barangay* officials and community residents regarding the level of involvement of *barangay tanods* in performing their duties and Responsibilities when grouped according to their municipalities

Dimensions	Municipality	Mean	F-value	P-value	Interpretation
Maintenance of peace and order	Cabagan	2.75	17.697	0.000	Significant
	San Pablo	3.79			
	Tumauini	3.48			
	Sto. Tomas	3.52			
	Delfin Albano	3.62			
	Sta. Maria	3.49			
Emergencies or disasters	Cabagan	2.90	12.084	0.000	Significant
	San Pablo	3.82			
	Tumauini	3.57			
	Sto. Tomas	3.55			
	Delfin Albano	3.65			
	Sta. Maria	3.55			
Handling complaints involving women	Cabagan	3.01	9.614	0.000	Significant
	San Pablo	3.82			
	Tumauini	3.44			
	Sto. Tomas	3.56			
	Delfin Albano	3.71			
	Sta. Maria	3.47			
Handling complaints involving children	Cabagan	2.94	6.495	0.000	Significant
	San Pablo	3.70			
	Tumauini	3.41			
	Sto. Tomas	3.34			
	Delfin Albano	3.71			
	Sta. Maria	3.48			

As reflected on the above table, there are significant differences across all dimensions, maintenance of peace and order, emergencies or disasters, handling complaints involving women, and handling complaints involving children as indicated by the p-values (all 0.000), which are less than the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that the perceived level of involvement of *barangay tanods* varies particularly among the municipalities.

Overall, the results imply that the level of *tanod* involvement varies significantly across municipalities, reflecting differences in local leadership, governance effectiveness, available resources, and training opportunities. Municipalities like San Pablo and Delfin Albano exhibit higher involvement levels, likely due to stronger institutional support and proactive community engagement. In contrast, Cabagan's consistently lower ratings across all dimensions suggest areas for improvement.

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that *barangay tanods* play an important role in fostering civic responsibility, fellowship, and public trust in their respective communities. There was evidence of the effectiveness of *barangay tanods* in meeting the requirements set forth by national policies; however, support from local leadership and adequate resources for *tanods* are essential for the success of this initiative. This study has shown that how community residents perceive and understand the role of *barangay tanods* will influence their level of respect for the service provided by the *tanods*. As a result, many residents need more community input, recognition of the contributions of *barangay tanods*, and increased training opportunities for *barangay tanods* to enhance their skills and meet the changing demands of the communities served by the *tanods*.

Overall, the findings of this study indicate that there is a need for continued compliance with existing policies, continued support from leadership, involvement of all members of the community, and provision of ongoing professional development for the improvement of the *barangay tanod* system in order to improve the grassroots peacekeeping capabilities of local residents.

V. RECOMMENDATION

The DILG and LGUs should implement standardized monitoring, evaluation, and auditing procedures in order to obtain compliance with the Omnibus Policy within the municipalities that fall under their jurisdiction. The support of these entities will also ensure that barangays are adequately funded and equipped with the necessary equipment described above. In order for barangays to generate awareness of the services provided by *tanods* and increase community participation, it is important for *tanod* officials to hold regular assemblies and conduct information campaigns within their communities which will create a sense of trust and will develop relationships among the residents. Training programs that address peacekeeping and disaster response should continue to be offered and standardized as well as provide additional social protection. A recommendation for the implementation of a Program-Based Omnibus Policy is designed to promote employment opportunities by defining clear qualifications and increasing benefits for *barangay tanods*, as well as improving administrative support. Future research should be conducted across a broader geographic area using qualitative methods in order to fully understand and assess the long-term impact of efforts to promote community safety and crime prevention.

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